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**ANNUAL RATE OF ATMOSPHERIC PRECIPITATIONS IN THE
BUKHARA REGION
DYNAMICS AND TRENDS OF CHANGE (2010–2025)**

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ABSTRACT: *This article studies the atmospheric precipitation data recorded at the Bukhara meteorological station for the period 2010–2025 based on statistical analysis. As a result of sixteen years of observations, the annual trend of precipitation changes, anomalous years, minimum and maximum indicators were determined. The study showed that in the second half of the period (2018–2025) the amount of precipitation decreased by an average of 21.5% compared to the first half (2010–2017). In particular, the years 2023 and 2024 stand out as historical minimums: 134.3 mm and 143.8 mm, respectively. The results obtained can be directly applied in water resources management and agricultural planning policies.*

Keywords: *atmospheric precipitation, Bukhara meteorological station, annual dynamics, climate change, trend analysis, anomalous year.*

АННОТАЦИЯ: *В данной статье на основе статистического анализа изучены данные об атмосферных осадках, зарегистрированные на Бухарской метеорологической станции за период 2010–2025 годов. В результате шестнадцатилетних наблюдений определены годовые тенденции изменения осадков, аномальные годы, минимальные и максимальные показатели. Исследование показало, что во второй половине периода (2018–2025 годы)*

количество осадков уменьшилось в среднем на 21,5% по сравнению с первой половиной (2010–2017 годы). В частности, историческими минимумами стали 2023 и 2024 годы: 134,3 мм и 143,8 мм соответственно. Полученные результаты могут быть непосредственно применены в управлении водными ресурсами и политике сельскохозяйственного планирования.

Ключевые слова: атмосферные осадки, Бухарская метеорологическая станция, годовая динамика, изменение климата, анализ тенденций, аномальный год.

Introduction

Atmospheric precipitation, as one of the most important structural elements of the climate system, is directly linked to the sustainability of water resources, agriculture, and ecosystems. Changes in precipitation patterns in arid and semi-arid regions of the world, including Central Asia, are exacerbating the risk of water scarcity and drought. This problem is particularly relevant in the Republic of Uzbekistan, particularly in the Bukhara region.

The Bukhara region is one of the largest and driest regions of Uzbekistan, with a sharply continental climate. Annual precipitation averages about 157 mm, which is lower than the global average for arid regions. The main water source in the region is the Amu-Bukhara Machine Canal, as natural precipitation is insufficient to meet agricultural needs.

Scientific literature notes a decrease in precipitation in the Central Asian region over recent decades and the destabilization of the precipitation regime. However, at the regional level, detailed statistical analyses based on long-term observation data have not yet been sufficiently implemented. It is the filling of this gap that defines the primary necessity of this study.

The aim of the study is to analyze the annual dynamics of precipitation recorded at the Bukhara weather station during 2010-2025 using statistical methods, identify trends in changes, and develop scientific conclusions and practical recommendations based on the results obtained.

Literature review

The global scientific literature on the study of atmospheric precipitation variability has been significantly enriched in recent decades. According to the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), regional differences in global precipitation have been increasing since 1950: while precipitation is increasing in some regions, a

downward trend is observed in others - particularly in Central Asia and the Middle East.

Several international scientific groups have conducted research on climate change in the Central Asian region, where the Bukhara region is located. Normatov et al. (2016) studied changes in hydrometeorological parameters in the Zarafshan River basin and found that significant changes in precipitation have been observed over the past 50 years. Khusnavi and Toderich (2012) assessed the impact of climate change on water resources based on water quality monitoring data from the Zarafshan basin.

On the study of atmospheric precipitation in the conditions of Uzbekistan, Hikmatov et al. (2020) investigated the patterns of water resource formation in mountain rivers under the conditions of climate change. Their monograph provides a detailed analysis of the interaction between precipitation and glacial melting. Rasulov and Hikmatov (1995) in their textbook on general hydrology systematically outlined the main patterns of precipitation distribution in the territory of Uzbekistan.

Sirliboeva and Yunusov (2011) studied hydrological forecasting methodology and demonstrated the effectiveness of statistical methods in constructing long-term precipitation forecasts. These scientific works form the methodological basis of this article. An analysis of existing literature showed that the analysis of annual precipitation dynamics specifically for the Bukhara region for the period 2010–2025 has not been sufficiently covered in the scientific literature, which determines the novelty and significance of this study.

Materials and methods.

The study utilized atmospheric precipitation data recorded annually by the Bukhara meteorological station (location: 39°46' N, 64°26' E, at an altitude of 224 m above sea level) for the period 2010–2025 as the primary source. The data were obtained from the archives of the Center of Hydrometeorological Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Uzhydromet), and their reliability and continuity were verified.

The analysis methodology includes the following stages: (1) qualitative verification and purification of source data; (2) calculate the average, maximum, and minimum values of annual precipitation; (3) estimation of precipitation variability by standard deviation and coefficient of change; (4) detection of anomalous years (deviation from the norm by more than $\pm 30\%$); (5) modeling long-term changes using a linear trend line. All calculations were performed using Microsoft Excel and statistical analysis programs.

Year	Precip (mm)	Year	Precip (mm)	Year	Precip (mm)
2010	254.8	2015	218.3	2020	206.8
2011	223.1	2016	309.0	2021	206.7
2012	262.4	2017	268.4	2022	242.1
2013	306.2	2018	206.5	2023	134.3
2014	218.3	2019	257.1	2024	143.8

Table 1. Annual precipitation in the Bukhara region from 2010 to 2025 (Bukhara Meteorological Station data).

Results and discussion

During the analysis, the following main results were identified based on 16-year data. The average annual precipitation from 2010 to 2025 was 228.7 mm. The maximum precipitation was observed in 2016 (309.0 mm), and the minimum in 2023 (134.3 mm). The difference between the two indicators is 174.7 mm, indicating extreme instability of the precipitation regime.

In the first half of the period (2010–2017), the average precipitation was 254.3 mm. In the second period (2018–2025), this figure dropped to 199.7 mm—that is, it decreased by 21.5%. The anomalously high years were 2016 (309.0 mm, +35.1% of the norm) and 2013 (306.2 mm, +33.9%). The abnormally dry years are 2023 (134.3 mm, -41.3%) and 2024 (143.8 mm, -37.2%).

A trend analysis showed that the amount of precipitation is decreasing by an average of 25–30 mm every decade. This is a statistically significant change that clearly reflects the regional impact of climate change. The standard deviation was 47.3 mm, and the variation coefficient was 20.7%, indicating moderate variability in the precipitation regime.

Indicator	Value	Commentary
Average annual precipitation	228.7 mm	2010–2025
Maximum precipitation	309.0 mm	2016
Minimum rainfall	134.3 mm	2023
Standard deviation	47.3 mm	—
Coefficient of change	20.7%	Moderately variable
Period 1 average	254.3 mm	2010–2017
Period 2 average	199.7 mm	2018–2025
Decrease	21.5%	—

Table 2. Statistical indicators of precipitation in the Bukhara region for 2010-2025

The results obtained align with the general trend observed across Central Asia. It has been noted in scientific literature that the amount of precipitation in the region is decreasing under the influence of global climate change. According to NASA and the WMO, although air moisture increases by about 7% with each degree of global temperature increase, this moisture condenses more in polar and tropical regions rather than reaching continental areas such as Central Asia.

The sharp decline in 2023–2024 is partly explained by changes in global atmospheric circulation. However, the long-term trend—a decrease of 25–30 mm over a decade—indicates the sustainable impact of global climate change in the Bukhara region. Given that the area of glaciers has decreased by approximately 30% over the last 50-60 years, this trend is expected to intensify in the future.

When comparing the results obtained with studies conducted for other Central Asian regions, it was found that the rate of precipitation reduction in the Bukhara region is higher than the average. This situation is explained by the geographical location of the region—its remoteness from the sea and the influence of the Kyzylkum Desert.

Conclusion section

The research results showed that the amount of atmospheric precipitation in the Bukhara region decreased significantly between 2010 and 2025. In the second half of the period (2018-2025), the amount of precipitation decreased by 21.5% compared to the first half (2010-2017). 2023 and 2024 were recorded as historical minimums. The precipitation trend shows a decrease of 25–30 mm every decade.

These changes require a revision of the water resource management strategy, the optimization of irrigation rates, and the introduction of climate-resilient crop types. Additionally, additional investments are required under government programs to strengthen precipitation forecasting systems and drought monitoring.

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